

УДК 504.3.054(479.22)

doi <https://doi.org/10.31996/mru.2025.2.89-94>

В. О. ЄМЕЛЬЯНОВ, чл.-кор. НАН України, д-р геол.-мін. наук, проф., голов. наук. співроб. (Державна наукова установа "Центр проблем морської геології, геоecології та осадового рудоутворення НАН України"), volodyasea1990@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8972-0754>,

Є. І. НАСЕДКІН, канд. геол. наук, ст. наук. співроб., ст. дослідник (Державна наукова установа "Центр проблем морської геології, геоecології та осадового рудоутворення НАН України", Інститут геологічних наук НАН України), nasedevg@ukr.net, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2633-9291>,

Т. С. КУКОВСЬКА, канд. геол.-мін. наук, ст. наук. співроб. (Державна наукова установа "Центр проблем морської геології, геоecології та осадового рудоутворення НАН України"), t.kukovska@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7532-8885>,

Н. О. ФЕДОРОНЧУК, канд. геол. наук, ст. наук. співроб., доц. (Державна наукова установа "Центр проблем морської геології, геоecології та осадового рудоутворення НАН України"), fedoronch@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4903-4928>,

С. М. ДОВБИШ, наук. співроб. (Інститут геологічних наук НАН України, Державна наукова установа "Центр проблем морської геології, геоecології та осадового рудоутворення НАН України"), dovbysh@ukr.net, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3542-7472>

V. IEMELIANOV, Corresponding Member of NAS of Ukraine, Doctor of Geological and Mineralogical Sciences, Professor, Chief Researcher Scientist (State Scientific Institution "Center for Problems of Marine Geology, Geoecology and Sedimentary Ore Formation of NAS of Ukraine"), volodyasea1990@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8972-0754>,

Ye. NASIEDKIN, PhD (Geology), Senior Researcher, Senior Researcher (State Scientific Institution "Center for Problems of Marine Geology, Geoecology and Sedimentary Ore Formation of NAS of Ukraine", Institute of Geological Sciences of NAS of Ukraine), nasedevg@ukr.net, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2633-9291>,

T. KUKOVSKA, PhD (Geol. & Mineral.), Senior Researcher (State Scientific Institution "Center for Problems of Marine Geology, Geoecology and Sedimentary Ore Formation of NAS of Ukraine"), t.kukovska@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7532-8885>,

N. FEDORONCHUK, PhD (Geology), Senior Researcher, Associate Professor (State Scientific Institution "Center for Problems of Marine Geology, Geoecology and Sedimentary Ore Formation of NAS of Ukraine"), fedoronch@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4903-4928>,

S. DOVBYSH, Researcher (Institute of Geological Sciences of NAS of Ukraine, State Scientific Institution "Center for Problems of Marine Geology, Geoecology and Sedimentary Ore Formation of NAS of Ukraine"), dovbysh@ukr.net, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3542-7472>

МІКРОПЛАСТИК У ГЕОЛОГО-ЕКОЛОГІЧНІЙ СУБСИСТЕМІ ПРИБЕРЕЖНОЇ ЧАСТИНИ ГЕОЕКОСИСТЕМИ ШЕЛЬФУ ГРУЗІЇ

MICROPLASTICS IN THE GEOLOGICAL-ECOLOGICAL SUBSYSTEM OF THE COASTAL PART OF THE GEOECOSYSTEM OF THE GEORGIAN SHELF

Представлено результати досліджень розподілу мікропластику в поверхневому шарі донних відкладів прилеглої до узбережжя Грузії акваторії, проведених фахівцями Державної наукової установи "МорGeoЕкоЦентр НАН України". Ці роботи є складовою масштабного міжнародного проекту DOORS у рамках програми Horizon 2020 з визначення вмісту та розподілу штучних полімерів у геоecосистемі Чорного моря. Протягом 2022–2024 рр. також досліджено вміст мікропластику в межах пляжевих і літоральних ділянок північно-західної частини моря, її шельфових частин, а також шельфу і материкового схилу в межах румунського сектору моря.

Результати робіт засвідчили присутність частинок мікропластику у складі поверхневих шарів середовища донних відкладів у межах усієї берегової смуги вздовж усього прибережжя від с. Гоніо до с. Кулеві. Розмірність виявлених фрагментів у середньому становила 100–300 мкм. За відсотковим розподілом серед різних видів полімерів, склад яких був підтверджений Раман-спектрометрією, домінували поліетилен і поліпропілен. Були також присутні одиничні фрагменти полістиролу. Крім того, проведені дослідження показали, що кількість частинок у порівнянні з результатами, отриманими при дослідженнях інших шельфових ділянок, у середньому на 50 % менша. Це може свідчити не тільки про вплив особливостей шельфу узбережжя Грузії та активних гідродинамічних процесів, але і про вплив інтенсивності емісії частинок з джерел надходження. Проведені роботи дозволили отримати важливий практичний досвід щодо визначення штучних полімерів у складі геологічного середовища геоecосистеми Чорного моря та вдосконалити застосовані методи досліджень відповідно до існуючих європейських стандартів.

Ключові слова: мікропластик, донні відклади, методика досліджень, екологія, спектроскопія, Чорне море, шельф Грузії.

The results of studies on the distribution of microplastics in the surface layer of seafloor sediments in the water area adjacent to the coast of Georgia, conducted by specialists of the State Scientific Institution "MorGeoEcoCenter of the NAS of Ukraine", are presented. These works are part of a large-scale international DOORS project within the framework of the program Horizon 2020 to determine the content and distribution of artificial polymers in the geoecosystem of the Black Sea. During 2022–2024, the content of microplastics was also studied within the beach and littoral areas of the northwestern part of the sea, its shelf areas, as well as the shelf and continental slope within the Romanian sector of the sea.

The results showed the presence of microplastic particles in the surface layers of seafloor sediments along the entire coastal zone from the village of Gonion to the village of Kulevi. The size of the detected fragments averaged 100–300 μm. According to the percentage distribution among different types of polymers, the composition of which was confirmed by Raman spectrometry, polyethylene and polypropylene predominated; single fragments of polystyrene were also present. At the same time, the studies showed that the number of particles, compared to the results obtained from studies of other shelf areas, was on average 50% less. This may indicate not only the influence of the features of the Georgian coastal shelf and active hydrodynamic processes, but also the influence of the intensity of particle emission from sources. The work carried out allowed us to gain valuable practical experience in determining artificial polymers in the geological environment of the Black Sea geoecosystem and improve the applied research methods in accordance with existing European standards.

Keywords: microplastics, seafloor sediments, research methodology, ecology, spectroscopy, Black Sea, Georgian Shelf.

Introduction

Distribution and accumulation of artificial polymers in the geocosystems of the seas and oceans is a recognized global problem, and the development of an effective strategy for managing plastic waste and minimizing its impact on the marine environment is impossible without direct research in the places of their entry and accumulation [3, 7].

The accumulation and systematization of information regarding detection of the quantity and assessment of the distribution of various forms and types of microplastics (MP) in the upper layer of seafloor sediments (SS) as part of the geological-ecological subsystem (GESS) that has formed and functions in various areas of the border with the aquatic subsystem (AqSS) of the geocosystem of the Black Sea (GESBS), opens up the possibility for a comprehensive assessment of the pathways of synthetic polymers entering the marine geological environment, their accumulation in it, as well as a better understanding of the corresponding accompanying processes.

Experts from the State Scientific Institution “MorGeoEco-Center” of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, particularly within the framework of the international project DOORS, conducted systematic studies of the MP content in specific parts of the geological environment of GESS of the GESBS, which have formed and function under appropriate ecological (geological, geographical, hydrological, hydrodynamic, etc.) conditions in 2022–2024. Beach and littoral areas of GESS in the northwestern part of the GESBS, its extensive shelf areas within the influence of fresh waters of the Danube River, as well as specific parts of the shelf and continental slope within the Romanian sector of the sea were studied [1, 8, 9, 10].

The latest expedition studies, the results of which are presented in this publication, were carried out in the shelf part of the Geo-Ecological Subsystem of the Black Sea (GESBS) with rather specific ecological (geographical, bathymetric, hydrological, etc.) conditions characteristic of its eastern part. It is known that the research area, located within the coastal shelf zone of Georgia, according to the relief of the border between corresponding spaces of the geological and aquatic subsystems of the GESBS, is characterized by a narrow shelf, relatively steep slopes of the sea bottom surface at the specified border and a large number of underwater canyons, which are underwater riverbeds that contribute to the transfer of sedimentary material from the shelf zone to the foot of continental slope [2].

As a result of synergy of active dynamic processes (gravitational, geological, hydrological, etc.), significant underwater landslides are formed here. It is believed that the smallest thicknesses of modern SS are confined to the axial parts of underwater valleys and canyons, the largest – to the alluvial cones within foot of the slopes. Thus, the presence of a narrow shelf and significant dissection of the continental slope by numerous canyons determine the complex nature of modern sedimentation processes, which are not uniformly implemented within different facial zones.

As per the ecological conditions of the land that have an impact on the emission of anthropogenic substances into marine environment, including plastic and MPs, one should mark a sufficiently dense river network and a significant amount of precipitation (usually on the slopes facing the Black Sea, their amount reaches 3000-4000 mm), which contributes to intensive removal of suspended matter to the coastal part of the GESBS space, that is recorded in satellite images as quite contrasting colored trails.

Regarding the most important sources of plastics entering marine environment in the GESBS parts within Georgia, they can be reasonably subdivided into two categories:

1. Sources located directly within the socio-economic subsystems, spatially situated either on the border with GESBS (settlements, recreational areas, etc.) or within its boundaries (port hubs, maritime transport, etc.) [4]. For example, Batumi, which is one of the largest Georgian resorts on the Black Sea coast and, at the same time, one of the largest Black Sea ports. It should be noted that to the north of Batumi, in the subtropical climate zone, 21 kilometers from Batumi, there is another major Georgian resort – Kobuleti. The small-pebble beaches of these resorts stretch for dozens of kilometers, forming a band of potential pollution of the marine environment by the household segment of plastics.

2. River transit, inflow of pollutants, particularly plastic and MPs, which occurs mainly via wastewater and stormwater from residential areas, industrial enterprises, official and unofficial landfills, etc. [14].

Georgia's territory is characterized by its belonging to the mountainous terrain of the mobile Alpine belt of the earth's crust, which results in a sharp change in relief, differences in heights and lowlands, high flow rates and intensity of currents of rivers flowing into the Black Sea within the Georgian coast, on a relatively small area. Among them, the largest river in western Georgia is Rioni with its tributaries, as well as large rivers such as Inguri, Kodori, Adjaristsqali and Khobi. At the same time, in the SS of the coastal zone, as a result of a sharp drop in depths and active landslides of the accumulated surface layer of sediments from the shelf part along the continental slope, active self-cleaning of SS also occurs. It is believed that due to hydrodynamics of the sea on the Georgian coast, the sharp drop in depths, and the presence of underwater canyons, pollutants do not linger in the coastal zone and are actively carried away to the deeper zones of water area.

Methodological aspects of conducting marine research, processing and analysis of samples

Bottom sediment sampling in 2024 was conducted within the framework of the international research project DOORS – “Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea” H2020. Samples were collected aboard the research vessel “Mare Nigrum” of the Romanian National Institute of Marine Geology and Geoecology (GeoEcoMar). Sampling was performed using a Van-Veen Grab (Hydro-Bios KIEL, 35×40 cm opening) directly at the GESS sites of the shelf geocosystem located along the Georgian coast at sea depths ranging from 25 m to 100 m (Fig. 1). For MP analysis, a surface and near-surface (boundary relative to AqSS) layer of GESS geological environment with a thickness of 0.05 m was sampled in natural measurement. Samples were collected into aluminum containers, stored and transported to the laboratory at temperature -18°C. 6 samples were analyzed using laboratory methods. Since the weight of the samples varied sig-

Fig. 1. The scheme of sampling points on the Georgian coast, 2024

nificantly depending on their water content, recalculation of the analysis results was subsequently performed on a dry weight basis.

Sample preparation procedure and analysis methodology, considering the necessity of applying an established methodological scheme in the analysis of SS from different areas of the Black Sea shelf, corresponded to the scheme used in previous studies [10].

The methodology of analytical studies conducted at the SSI “MorGeoEcoCenter” of the NAS of Ukraine was generally close to the relevant methodological recommendations, in particular (Fig. 2) [6, 12].

Sample preparation procedure included: drying without prior sieving, flotation in zinc chloride solution and selection of the lightest component, repeated sedimentation and separation in a separatory funnel, exposure to hydrogen peroxide, isopropyl alcohol treatment. Samples were washed with distilled water and dried after each of the above procedures. Considering the density of the most common categories of plastic polymers (ranging from 0.8 to 1.4 g/cm³) and the sediment matrix (more than 2.5 g/cm³), a solution for separating the mineral component and microplastic particles using zinc chloride (at a density of 1.8 g/cm³) was used in our studies. Minimization of the amount of natural organic suspended matter was achieved by sedimentation in a concentrated 35% hydrogen peroxide solution [11, 13].

Filtration processes at each stage of sample preparation were carried out through a polyamide filter cloth with a cell diameter of 36 μm. This corresponds to the recommended MP sizes for research, provided in the manual [6]. Direct determination of potential pollutants was based on visual characterization using optical instruments (microscope, magnifying glass, etc.). Visual identification of MP particles was performed under a SIGETA MB-12 LCD optical microscope monocle, according to a number of methods presented in the literature [15].

The main identifying indicators were color, the ratio of linear dimensions, and particle morphology.

Laboratory works on confirming the nature of MPs and determining their types were carried out using a single-cascade spectrometer MDR-23 equipped with a cooled CCD detector (Andor iDus 420, UK) and “Micromed” microscope. Raman spectra were excited by the radiation of solid-state lasers with wavelengths of 457, 532, 671 and 785 nm.

When identifying the plastic, an alternative identification method was also used – the hot needle test [5]. The necessity of using a thermal method was caused by significant difficulties in measuring on spectrometer such potential polymer fragments as fibers, the thickness of which did not exceed 10-20 μm. Simultaneously, the length of such fibers allowed for the performance of their thermal testing using a method considered quite reliable for counting synthetic polymers, but at the same time does not allow confirmation of their chemical composition and their assignment to some known MP categories. In this case, colorless (transparent, white, matte) fragments of linear form were not considered as potential MP particles, given the low level (less than 20%) of their confirmation as polymers in previous studies [10].

Fig. 2. Laboratory testing scheme in the cycle: sampling – final MP count and determination of their chemical types

Fig. 3. General appearance of some unverified objects, outwardly attributed to the category of possible MP particles. The first row – linear objects

On average, the fixed total number of fragments of natural hard mineral and organic matter and matter of anthropogenic origin, ranging in size from 1000 to 36 μm, in the processed samples exceeded 1000 specimens on average. The samples showed a large number of carbon particles, likely of woody origin. An undesirable background was also constituted by fragments of plants, including bark, stems and branches, reaching dimensions up to 10 mm and not subjected to treatment with hydrogen peroxide and acid. The amount of matter identified as MP and represented mainly by fibers, fiber fragments, films, granules and spherules was moderate. Most of them were colored (Fig. 3).

Results of the research and their discussion

The analysis of the research results confirmed that MP is present in all selected samples. When recalculated to 0.2 kg of dry matter of the sample, the concentrations of MP range from 5 to 19 particles per sample (Fig. 4). In the morphological types that were subdivided into linear objects (fibers) and flat/volumetric fragments, a relatively stable number (approximately five to six confirmed units for each sample) consisted of fibers. It should be noted that the category “linear objects” is not considered when determining the distribution of chemical types of MPs in samples collected from different locations, due to the verification methodology. Therefore, their assessment was based on the confirmed indicators of MPs classified into the second category.

Regarding color dominance, three main colorations with shades were characteristic for linear objects: red (orange, pink, etc.) accounted for 50%, blue (turquoise, light blue, pale blue, etc.) – 40%, green (light green, dirty green) – 10%. Black and transparent (matte) colored fibers were not included into the count due to low confirmation rates (less than 10%).

Fig. 4. Diagrams: a) Distribution of the total number of particles (pcs) of MP (fragments and fibers) in different samples. The sample from station S3B was taken on the shelf in the area of Rioni river’s water discharge, from station S3C – river Hobby; b) Relative content of different morphological types of polymers within their total number

Among the features that highlight the connection of the distribution of MP with external conditions, it is worth noting, for example, the sufficiently clear linkage of the maximum concentrations of detected polymer particles to the areas of inflow and unloading of the mouth parts of rivers, in particular the Rioni River and the Khobi River. On one hand, this is a clearly expected trend of limited influence of runoff from small rivers within the space of narrow shelf areas. On the other hand, the active hydrodynamic processes characteristic of the geocosystem space of narrow shelf areas significantly affect the self-purification of their coastal parts by means of the export of substances into the adjacent open space of GESBS, and the accumulation of such substances in the geological environment of GESS, which are formed and function at a certain distance from the river mouth locations, even within the GESS space of the continental slope.

The fact of active accumulation in the geological environment of the GESS discharge areas in the sea of a large amount of suspended particles, which are usually kept afloat, is confirmed by the substantial number (more than 1000 pieces per sample) of fragments of plants and wood, which during the extraction was a “visiting card” for all samples of the geological environment of GESS in this part of the GESBS (Fig. 5).

Among the features of the distribution of granulometric fractions of the substance, it should be noted the dominance of wood/plant residues only in the fraction of 0.5–0.1 cm. Finer particles are mostly represented by the mineral component, carbon particles, and, presumably, fragments of marine organisms. Regarding the content of nonlinear MP fragments in the composition of the 0.5–0.1 cm fraction, it should be noted that only two units were present across all analyzed samples belonging to station S3-2 (Fig. 6).

Fig. 5. The S3-2 station is located in close proximity to the mouth of the Rioni River. a) A fragment of the map showing the location of the S3-2 station on the shelf and the features of the coastal area; the map clearly shows the intrusion of suspended flows from the Rioni River into the waters of the Black Sea; b) A general photo of the substance separated from the SS, where fragments larger than 3 mm consisted exclusively of wooden remains; c) A photograph from a microscope lens showing the composition features of the fine-dispersed substance after the removal of fragments larger than 300 microns

Fig. 6. Representative samples with dimensions exceeding 1 mm: a) station S3-2, flat particle made of polyethylene (PE); b) fragment of a linear object (station S3-2, made of polypropylene (PP))

Fig. 7. A part of PP (a) particle and its spectrum (b) (confirmation on a Raman spectrometer). It is clearly visible that the polymer fragment is almost entirely covered with a crust of chemical or organic nature, and the peaks of PP are barely discernible against the background of intense photoluminescence

Regarding the distribution of different types of polymers within the fraction of 36–1000 μm , it should be noted that PP particles predominated (70%), followed by PE (25%) and to a significantly lesser extent polystyrene (PS) (5%). It is also necessary to mention that the results confirming the nature of the samples on Raman spectrometer do not always yield positive results when measuring polymer particles. This can significantly affect the overall research results and may be related to physico-chemical changes on the surface of the samples due to prolonged exposure to marine environment, as well as the component content of the particle itself, particularly the presence of dyes or various additives in the polymer composition.

For example, in Fig. 7, a Raman spectrum from one of the sample points is presented, while intense photoluminescence (PL) is recorded at other points. This is clearly manifested when exciting the spectra with radiation at a wavelength of 457 nm. The small intensity Raman peaks present in the PL spectrum indicate (according to their frequency position) that this fragment is PP. This comparison clearly demonstrates how intense PL “masks” the Raman bands. At the same time, when magnifying the sample under a microscope, one can observe formations of organic or chemical nature on its surface, which are likely the cause of such errors during verification.

A fact worth final highlighting is a significant amount of carbon particles in the samples collected along the coastline. Thus, for some separated samples, it constitutes 2/3 of the material in the size fraction <1 mm. The largest number of carbon particles is observed in the sample from the S3C station, located on the shelf near the mouth of Hobi River into the Black Sea (within the village of Kulevi).

Conclusions

Today, actually in Ukraine and the world, there are few studies on the migration features of MP from its sources to the accumulation sites in the geological environment of the continental slope, shelf, and beach parts of the Ocean’s geocosystem, including the Black Sea geocosystem as its component. The accumulation and systematization of information on determining the quantitative assessment, features and patterns of distribution of microplastic forms and types within different areas of GESS geosystem, in particular the Black Sea as a component of the Ocean geosystem, opens up the possibility of a comprehensive assessment of the pathways of artificial polymers entering the geological environment of the latter and the processes of their accumulation in it. The conducted studies of the shelf GESSBS

area within the coast of Georgia are of particular value due to the unique relief of the border between GESS and AqSS, on a narrow shelf, which within a few kilometers turns into a continental slope dissected by deep canyons. Since the plumes of freshened river waters, which are well identifiable on satellite images, usually extend beyond the shelf here, it is logical to expect the transfer of a significant part of microplastics to the deep-water areas of GESS continental slope.

The results of our work have confirmed the presence of MP particles in the composition of the surface layers of GESS environment along the entire coastline from the village of Gonio to the village of Kulevi. At the same time, the conducted studies showed that the number of particles, for example, compared to the results obtained in studies on other shelf areas of GESS, particularly those located within the territorial waters of Romania, is on average some 50% lower. This may indicate not only the influence of specified features of the relief of border between GESS and AqSS and hydrodynamic processes but also manifestation of the intensity of particle emissions from their input sources.

The size of identified fragments averaged 100-300 μm, with individual specimens reaching 1,5–3 mm. In terms of morphological characteristics, volumetric/flat fragments and fibers constituted approximately equal amounts. In the percentage redistribution among different types of polymers, the composition of which was confirmed by Raman spectroscopy, PE and PP predominated; single fragments of PS were also present.

Finally, it should be noted that the conducted exploration allowed not only to gain valuable practical experience in determining synthetic polymers in the geological environment of GESSBS system and to outline and apply a set of research methods in accordance with the existing European standards, but also to directly assess the content and distribution of MPs in different environmentally conditioned areas of GESSBS located on the Caucasian coast. At the same time, identification of the distribution features of MPs and other synthetic polymers in the GES Black Sea geo-ecosystem environment is a current and relevant scientific task aimed at solving a number of academic and applied ecological, medical, and other issues, primarily the impact of seas and oceans on human health through the existing and known food chains.

Acknowledgments

The research in this area and the corresponding publication were made possible by the authors' participation in the international DOORS project. DOORS (<https://www.doorsblacksea.eu/>) received funding from the European Union Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020 under grant agreement No. 101000518.

ЛІТЕРАТУРА

1. Ємельянов В., Наседкін Є., Іванік О., Куковська Т., Юхимчук В., Мітрофанова О. Особливості розподілу макро- та мікропластику в межах пляжевих зон внутрішньоконтинентальних морів (на прикладі пляжевої зони м. Южне, Україна) // Вісн. КНУ ім. Тараса Шевченка. Геологія. – 2024. – Т. 3, № 1 (104). – С. 86–98. <https://doi.org/10.17721/1728-2713.104>
2. Ємельянов В. А., Мітропольський А. Ю., Наседкін Е. И., Пасынков А. А., Степаняк Ю. Д., Шнюкова Е. Е. Геоекологія чорноморського шельфа України. – Київ: Академперіодика, 2004. – 296 с.
3. Andrady A.L. Microplastics in the marine environment // *Marine Pollution Bulletin*. – 2011. – Vol. 62 (8). – P. 1596–1605. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2011.05.030>
4. Andrady A. L. Persistence of Plastic Litter in the Oceans // Bergmann M., Gutow L., Klages M. (Eds.). *Marine Anthropogenic Litter*. – Springer, Cham., 2015. – P. 57–72. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-16510-3_3
5. De Witte B., Devriese L., Bekaert K., Hoffman S., Vandermeersch G., Cooreman K., Robbens K. Quality assessment of the blue

mussel (*Mytilus edulis*): Comparison between commercial and wild types // *Marine Pollution Bulletin*. – 2014. – Vol. 85 (1). – P. 146–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.06.006>

6. Galgani F., Ruiz Orejon Sanchez Pastor L., Ronchi F., Zeri C., Fortibuoni T., Hanke G., Zorzo P., Gago J. Guidance on the Monitoring of Marine Litter in European Seas An update to improve the harmonized monitoring of marine litter under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. – Publications Office of the European Union, 2023. – 195 p. <https://doi.org/10.2760/59137>

7. Hidalgo-Ruz V., Gutow L., Thompson R.C., Thiel M. Microplastics in the Marine Environment: A Review of the Methods Used for Identification and Quantification // *Environmental Science and Technology*. – 2012. – No. 46 (6). – P. 3060–3075. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es2031505>

8. Iemelianov V.O., Nasiedkin Ye.L., Kukovska T.S., Mytrofanova O.A., Dovbysh S.M. Research of Plastics and Microplastics in the Black Sea Geoecosystem as a Component of Its Pollution Assessment // *Ukrainian geographical journal*. – 2023. – No. 4 (124). – P. 26–36. <https://doi.org/10.15407/ugz2023.04.027>

9. Iemelianov V., Nasiedkin Ye., Kukovska T., Yukhimchuk V., Fedoronchuk N., Mytrofanova O. Integrated approaches to monitoring microplastics in the geological component of marine environment // *Monitoring of geological processes and ecological condition of the environment. XVII International Scientific Conference, Kyiv, Ukraine, November 7–10, 2023*. – Kyiv, 2023. – P. 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.3997/2214-4609.2023520107>

10. Iemelianov Volodymyr, Nasiedkin Yevhen, Kukovska Tamara, Koshliakova Tetiana, Fedoronchuk Natalia, Shuraiev Ihor, Yukhimchuk Volodymyr. Exploring the microplastics distribution in the bottom sediments of the western Black Sea // *Visnyk of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Geology*. – 2024. – Vol. 4 (107). – P. 104–113. <http://doi.org/10.17721/1728-2713.10713>

11. Imhof H. K., Schmid J., Niessner R., Ivleva N. P., Laforsch C. A novel, highly efficient method for the separation and quantification of plastic particles in sediments of aquatic environments // *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods*. – 2012. – Vol. 10 (7). – P. 524–537. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lom.2012.10.524>

12. Masura J., Baker J., Foster G., Arthur C. Laboratory methods for the analysis of microplastics in the marine environment: recommendations for quantifying synthetic particles in waters and sediments (NOAA Technical Memorandum NOS-OR&R-48). – 2015. – 31 p. <http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-604>

13. Nuelle M.-T., Dekiff J.H., Remy D., Fries E. A new analytical approach for monitoring microplastics in marine sediments // *Environmental Pollution*. – 2014. – Vol. 184. – P. 161–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2013.07.027>

14. Tramoy R., Gasperi J., Dris R., Colasse L. Assessment of the Plastic Inputs From the Seine Basin to the Sea Using Statistical and Field Approaches // *Frontiers in Marine Science*. – April 2019. – Vol. 6. – P. 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00151>

15. Vermeiren P., Muñoz C., Ikejima K. Microplastic identification and quantification from organic rich sediments: A validated laboratory protocol // *Environmental Pollution*. – July 2020. – Vol. 262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.114298>

REFERENCES

1. Emelyanov V., Nasedkin E., Ivanik O., Kukovska T., Yukhimchuk V., Mitrofanova O. Peculiarities of the distribution of macro- and microplastics within the beach zones of inland seas (on the example of the beach zone of Yuzhne, Ukraine) // *Bulletin of the Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Geology*. – 2024. – Vol. 3, No. 1 (104). – P. 86–98. <http://doi.org/10.17721/1728-2713.104> (In Ukrainian).
2. Yemelyanov V. A., Mitropolsky A. Yu., Nasedkin E. I., Pasyнков A. A., Stepanyak Yu. D., Shnyukova E. E. Geoeology of the Black Sea shelf of Ukraine. – Kyiv: Akademperiodika, 2004. – 296 p. (In Russian).
3. Andrady A. L. Microplastics in the marine environment // *Marine Pollution Bulletin*. – 2011. – Vol. 62 (8). – P. 1596–1605. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2011.05.030>
4. Andrady A. L. Persistence of Plastic Litter in the Oceans // Bergmann M., Gutow L., Klages M. (Eds.). *Marine Anthropogenic Litter*. – Springer, Cham., – 2015. – P. 57–72. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-16510-3_3
5. De Witte B., Devriese L., Bekaert K., Hoffman S., Vandermeersch G., Cooreman K., Robbens K. Quality assessment of the blue mussel (*Mytilus edulis*): Comparison between commercial and wild types // *Marine Pollution Bulletin*. – 2014. – Vol. 85 (1). – P. 146–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.06.006>

6. Galgani F, Ruiz Orejon Sanchez Pastor L., Ronchi F, Zeri C., Fortibuoni T., Hanke G., Zorzo P., Gago J. Guidance on the Monitoring of Marine Litter in European Seas An update to improve the harmonized monitoring of marine litter under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. – Publications Office of the European Union, 2023. – 195 p. <https://doi.org/10.2760/59137>

7. Hidalgo-Ruz V., Gutow L., Thompson R. C., Thiel M. Microplastics in the Marine Environment: A Review of the Methods Used for Identification and Quantification // *Environmental Science and Technology*. – 2012. – No. 46 (6). – P. 3060–3075. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es2031505>

8. Iemelianov V. O., Nasiedkin Ye. I., Kukovska T. S., Mytrofanova O. A., Dovbysh S. M. Research of Plastics and Microplastics in the Black Sea Geocosystem as a Component of Its Pollution Assessment // *Ukrainian geographical journal*. – 2023. – No. 4 (124). – P. 26–36. <https://doi.org/10.15407/ugz2023.04.027>

9. Iemelianov V., Nasiedkin Ye., Kukovska T., Yukhymchuk V., Fedoronchuk N., Mytrofanova O. Integrated approaches to monitoring microplastics in the geological component of marine environment // *Monitoring of geological processes and ecological condition of the environment*. XVII International Scientific Conference, Kyiv, Ukraine, November 7–10, 2023. – Kyiv, 2023. – P. 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.3997/2214-4609.2023520107>

10. Iemelianov Volodymyr, Nasiedkin Yevhen, Kukovska Tamara, Koshliakova Tetiana, Fedoronchuk Natalia, Shuraiev Ihor, Yukhymchuk Volodymyr. Exploring the microplastics distribution in the bottom sediments of the western Black Sea // *Visnyk of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Geology*. – 2024. – Vol. 4 (107). P. 104–113. <http://doi.org/10.17721/1728-2713.10713>

11. Imhof H. K., Schmid J., Niessner R., Ivleva N. P., Laforsch C. A novel, highly efficient method for the separation and quantification of plastic particles in sediments of aquatic environments // *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods*. – 2012. – Vol. 10 (7). – P. 524–537. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lom.2012.10.524>

12. Masura J., Baker J., Foster G., Arthur C. Laboratory methods for the analysis of microplastics in the marine environment: recommendations for quantifying synthetic particles in waters and sediments (NOAA Technical Memorandum NOS-OR&R-48). – 2015. – 31 p. <http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-604>

13. Nuelle M.-T., Dekiff J.H., Remy D., Fries E. A new analytical approach for monitoring microplastics in marine sediments // *Environmental Pollution*. – 2014. – Vol. 184. – P. 161–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2013.07.027>

14. Tramoy R., Gasperi J., Dris R., Colasse L. Assessment of the Plastic Inputs From the Seine Basin to the Sea Using Statistical and Field Approaches // *Frontiers in Marine Science*. – April 2019. – Vol. 6. – P. 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00151>

15. Vermeiren P., Muñoz C., Ikejima K. Microplastic identification and quantification from organic rich sediments: A validated laboratory protocol // *Environmental Pollution*. – July 2020. – Vol. 262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.114298>

Рукопис отримано 18.04.2025.

ДО ВІДОМА АВТОРІВ

МІНЕРАЛЬНІ РЕСУРСИ УКРАЇНИ

ДЛЯ ПОДАЛЬШОГО ПІДВИЩЕННЯ НАУКОВОГО РЕЙТИНГУ ЖУРНАЛУ ТА ЙОГО ДОПИСУВАЧІВ ВАРТО ЗВЕРНУТИ УВАГУ НА ТАКЕ:

1. Кожна публікація не англійською мовою супроводжується анотацією англійською мовою обсягом не менш як 1800 знаків (з ключовими словами). Якщо видання не є повністю українськомовним, кожна публікація не українською мовою супроводжується анотацією українською мовою обсягом не менш як 1800 знаків (з ключовими словами, враховуючи пропуски).

2. Вимоги до анотацій англійською мовою: інформативність (без загальних слів); змістовність (відображення основного змісту статті та результатів досліджень); застосування термінології, характерної для іноземних спеціальних текстів; єдність термінології в межах анотації; без повторення відомостей, що містяться в заголовку статті.

3. Прізвища авторів статей надаються в одній із прийнятих міжнародних систем транслітерації (з української — відповідно до Постанови Кабінету Міністрів України № 55 від 27.01.2010 “Про впорядкування транслітерації українського алфавіту латиницею”, з російської — відповідно до “Системы транслитерации Библиотеки конгресса США”). Зазначення прізвища в різних системах транслітерації призводить до створення в базі даних різних профілів (ідентифікаторів) одного автора.

4. Для повного і коректного створення профілю автора дуже важливо вказати місце його роботи. Дані про публікації автора використовуються для отримання повної інформації щодо наукової діяльності організації і загалом країни. Застосування в статті офіційної, без скорочень, назви організації англійською мовою запобігатиме втраті статей у системі аналізу організацій та авторів. Бажано вказати в назві організації відомство, якому вона підпорядковується.

5. В аналітичній системі SCOPUS потрібні пристатейні списки використаної літератури латиницею. Можливості SCOPUS дають змогу проводити такі дослідження: за покликаннями оцінювати значення визнання робіт конкретних авторів, науковий рівень журналів, організацій і країн загалом, визначати актуальність наукових напрямів і проблем. Стаття з представленим списком літератури демонструє професійну ерудицію та якісний рівень досліджень її авторів.

6. Правильний опис джерел, на які покликаються автори, є запорукою того, що цитовану публікацію буде враховано в процесі оцінювання наукової діяльності її авторів, а отже, й організації, регіону, країни. За статистикою цитування журналу визначають його науковий рівень, авторитетність тощо. Тому найважливішими складниками в бібліографічних покликаннях є прізвища авторів і назви журналів. До опису статті треба вносити прізвища всіх авторів, не скорочуючи їхньої кількості. Для уникнення неточностей в ідентифікації авторства і визначення персональних метрик (показників) бібліометрії авторам наукових публікацій потрібно використовувати персональні коди ORCID.

7. Для українсько- та російськомовних статей з журналів, збірників, матеріалів конференцій структура бібліографічного опису така: автори (транслітерація), переклад назви статті англійською мовою, назва джерела (транслітерація), вихідні дані, у дужках — мова оригіналу, ідентифікатор DOI.

8. Список використаної літератури (References) для SCOPUS та інших закордонних баз даних наводиться повністю окремим блоком, повторюючи список літератури, що подається українською/російською мовою, незалежно від того, містяться в ньому чи ні іноземні джерела. Якщо в списку є покликання на іноземні публікації, їх повністю повторюють у списку, який створюють латиницею.

Рукопис статті до редакції автори подають зі своїми підписами.